

Supplementary file

Framing Food Online Discourse: Employing Generative AI and Semantic Analysis for Digital Lexicography and Terminology Extraction

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Supplementary Table 1. Greeklish mappings as identified in the present study (the Greek letter /sound is followed by the Latin letter(s) that take its place during Greeklish transliteration). The pronunciation of the Greek letters/digraphs is also provided, as it affects the transliterating process.

α (/a/) > a	β (/v/) > b, v	γ (/y/, /j/) > g	δ (/ð/) > d, th	ε (/e/) > e	ζ (/z/) > z
η (/i/) > i, e, h	θ (/θ/) > th	ι (/i/) > i	κ (/k/) > k	λ (/l/) > l	μ (/m/) > m
ν (/n/) > n	ξ (/ks/) > ks, x	ο (/o/) > o	π (/p/) > p	ρ (/r/) > r	σ (/s/) > s
τ (/t/) > t	υ (/i/) > y, i	φ (/f/) > f, ph	χ (/h/, /ç/) > ch, h, x	ψ (/ps/) > ps	ω (/o/) > o
αι (/e/) > ai, e	ει (/i/) > ei, i	οι (/i/) > oi, i	αυ (/av/, /af/) > av, au, af	ευ (/ev, ef/) > ev, eu, ef	ου (/u/) > ou
μπ (/b/) > b, mp	ντ (/d/, /nd/) > d, nt	γκ (/g/) > gg, gk, g	τσ (/ts/) > ts	τζ (/dz/) > tz	

Supplementary Table 2. Specific hashtags used to collect cheese related posts on Instagram. The Table shows all variations in Greeklish, Greek (correct and misspelled), and English (correct and misspelled).

Greek local cheeses	hashtags	non-Greek cheeses	hashtags
PDO Ladotyri of Mytilene	ladotyrimytilinis ladotyrimytilinis ladotyrimytilini ladotyri_cheese ladotyrimytilene ladotirimytilene ladotirimitilinis ladotirimitilini λαδοτύριμυτιλήνης λαδοτυριμυτιληνης λαδοτύριμυτιλίνης λαδοτύρι_μυτιλήνης λαδοτύρι_μυτιλλήνης	Gouda	κασεριgouda
Mastelo® of Chios	mastello tyrichiou mastelocheese μαστελο μαστέλο μαστελοχιου μαστελο_χιου μαστελο_χιωτικο	Edam	ενταμ ένταμ edam edamcheese
PDO Kalathaki of Lemnos	kalathakilimnou kalathakilemnos kalathakilemnou kalathaki_limnou kalathakilimnoscheese καλαθακιλημου καλαθάκιλήμου καλαθάκι_λήμου	Regatto	ρεγκατο ρεγκάτο
PDO Feta of Lemnos	fetalimnou feta_limnou	Mozzarella	μοτσαρέλα μοτσαρελα μοτσαρέλατυρί motsarela
Anthotyro of Lemnos	anthotyrolimnou anthotirolimnou	Emmental	έμενταλ εμενταλ
PDO Kasseri of Mytilene	κασέρι_μυτιλήνης	Parmesan	παρμεζάνα παρμεζανα
Kefalotyri of Mytilene	κεφαλοτυριμυτιληνης kefalotyrimytilinis	Blue cheese, Roquefort, Gorgonzola	ροκφορ ροκφόρ γκοργκοντζόλα γκοργκοντζολα
Melichloro of Lemnos	melichlorolimnou melichloro_limnou melihloro melihlorocheeselemnosgreece melihlorocheese melixloro melixloro_limnou melichloro	Cheddar	τσένταρ τσένταρ

	μελίχλωρο μελιχλωρο μελιχλωροτυριλημνου μελιχλωρολημνου		
Kathoura of Icaria	καθούρα καθουρα kathoura kathouracheese	Cottage	κότατζ κοτατζ
(other hashtags searched for)	anthotyros anthotyro_cheese ανθότυρο ανθοτυρο ανθότυρος ανθοτυρος limnoscheese lemnoscheese chioscheese samoscheese graviera γραβιέρα γραβιερα κεφαλοτυρι κεφαλοτύρι kefalotyri kefalotyricheese kefalotiri kefalotiricheese kefalotiri_cheese myzhthra myzithra myzithracheese myzithra_cheese mizithra mizithracheese mizithra_cheese μυζήθρα μυζηθρα μυζηθραξερη μυζήθραξηρη μυζήθρα_ξερη mytilinicheese τυριάμυτιλήνης cheese mytilini cheese mytilene cheese samos cheese ikaria cheese chios cheese xios cheese limnos cheese lemnos		

Supplementary Table 3. Example of the top 10 most frequent hashtags for the category CheeseVariety (excerpt). The full tables, including all categories for both local and non-Greek cheeses, and snails are provided in the online repository¹ [link: <https://zenodo.org/records/17306360>].

Local cheeses		Non-Greek cheeses	
Hashtags	Frequency	Hashtags	Frequency
Graviera	6508	Mozzarella	540
Cheese	4374	Parmesan	532
Mizithra	3104	Gouda	231
Kefalotyri	2399	Cheddar	199
GreekCheese	1475	Cheese	175
Feta	1464	Feta	49
Anthotyro	684	Graviera	20
Manouri	327	Manouri	10
Halloumi	157	Ricotta	9
Gruyere	148	Anthotyro	8

Note: Normalized outcome (Greek, Greeklish, English variants merged under one canonical English form). Normalization mapping:

Cheese Varieties

- **Graviera**
 - Greek: γραβιέρα
 - Greeklish: graviera, graviéra, graviera_crete
 - English: graviera
 - **Normalized form: Graviera**
- **Feta**
 - Greek: φέτα
 - Greeklish: feta, pheta
 - English: feta
 - **Normalized form: Feta**
- **Mizithra**
 - Greek: μιζήθρα, μιζύθρα
 - Greeklish: mizithra, mizythra, mizithra_cheese
 - English: mizithra
 - **Normalized form: Mizithra**
- **Kefalotyri**

¹ Files provided in online repository:

1) Cheese_Hashtags_COMPARATIVE_FINAL.xlsx

- Comparative (Local vs Non-Greek). Logic-first categorization.
- CheeseVariety: ONLY actual cheeses; Greek/Greeklish/English variants merged to canonical English.
- FoodPairing: dishes/ingredients (pizza, chicken, salad, bread); not treated as varieties.
- README sheet explains the logic succinctly.

2) Snails_Hashtags_FINAL.xlsx

- Logic-first categorization; NO normalization (hashtags preserved as collected).
- README sheet; Counts_PerCategory (if available); All_Categorized reconstruction; verbatim per-category sheets.

- Greek: κεφαλοτύρι
- Greeklish: kefalotyri, kefalotiri
- English: kefalotyri
→ **Normalized form: Kefalotyri**
- **Halloumi**
 - Greek: χαλλούμι
 - Greeklish: halloumi, xaloumi
 - English: halloumi
→ **Normalized form: Halloumi**
- **Manouri**
 - Greek: μανούρι
 - Greeklish: manouri
 - English: manouri
→ **Normalized form: Manouri**
- **Mozzarella**
 - Greek: μοτσαρέλα, μοτσαρελα
 - Greeklish: mozzarella, mozzarella, motzarella
 - English: mozzarella
→ **Normalized form: Mozzarella**
- **Parmesan**
 - Greek: παρμεζάνα, παρμεζανα
 - Greeklish: parmezana, parmesana
 - English: parmesan
→ **Normalized form: Parmesan**
- **Gouda**
 - Greek: γκούντα, γκουντα
 - Greeklish: gouda, gkounta
 - English: gouda
→ **Normalized form: Gouda**
- **Cheddar**
 - Greek: τσένταρ, τσενταρ
 - Greeklish: tsentar, tsentar_cheese
 - English: cheddar
→ **Normalized form: Cheddar**

Generic / Category Terms

- **Cheese**
 - Greek: τυρί, τυρια
 - Greeklish: tyri, tiri
 - English: cheese
→ **Normalized form: Cheese**
- **GreekCheese**
 - Greeklish: greekcheese, elliniko_tyri
 - English: greekcheese
→ **Normalized form: GreekCheese**

Supplementary Table 4. TBX and OntoLex-lemon representations of “graviera”.

TBX representation of “graviera”	OntoLex-lemon representation of “graviera”
<pre> <termEntry id="t_graviera"> <langSet xml:lang="en"> <tig> <term>graviera cheese</term> <descrip type="definition"> A hard yellow Greek cheese, traditionally made from sheep’s milk or a mixture of sheep and goat milk, recognized as a Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) product in Crete and Naxos. </descrip> <descrip type="frame">Consumption</descrip> <descrip type="frameElement">CheeseVariety</descrip> <descrip type="origin">Crete, Naxos</descrip> <descrip type="occasion">meze, dinner, holiday meal</descrip> <descrip type="foodPairing">wine, pasta, salad</descrip> <descrip type="assessment">authentic, traditional, tasty, PDO</descrip> <descrip type="emotion">nostalgia, pride, enjoyment</descrip> <admin type="status">preferredTerm</admin> <admin type="subjectField">food science, gastronomy</admin> </tig> </langSet> </termEntry> </pre>	<pre> @prefix ontolex: <http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/ontolex#> . @prefix lexinfo: <http://www.lexinfo.net/ontology/3.0/lexinfo#> . @prefix vartrans: <http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/vartrans#> . @prefix lime: <http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/lime#> . @prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> . @prefix dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> . @prefix ex: <http://example.org/cheese/> . ##### Frame & frame-element style hooks (domain ontology layer) ex:ConsumptionFrame a ex:Frame ; skos:prefLabel "Consumption"@en . # FE-like properties used to encode roles ex:hasOrigin a owl:ObjectProperty . ex:hasOccasion a owl:ObjectProperty . ex:hasFoodPairing a owl:ObjectProperty . ex:hasAssessment a owl:ObjectProperty . ex:hasEmotion a owl:ObjectProperty . ex:hasVariety a owl:ObjectProperty . ##### Concept for Graviera (terminological/ontological node) ex:GRAVIERA a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "Graviera (cheese)"@en ; skos:altLabel "γρᾰβιέρᾰ"@el ; skos:definition "Hard yellow Greek cheese, traditionally made from sheep’s milk or mixed sheep- goat milk; PDO in Crete and Naxos."@en ; dct:subject ex:ConsumptionFrame ; ex:hasVariety ex:CheeseVariety ; ex:hasOrigin ex:Crete , ex:Naxos ; ex:hasOccasion ex:Meze , ex:Dinner , ex:HolidayMeal ; ex:hasFoodPairing ex:Wine , ex:Pasta , ex:Salad ; ex:hasAssessment ex:Authentic , ex:Traditional , ex:Tasty , ex:PDO ; ex:hasEmotion ex:Nostalgia , ex:Pride , ex:Enjoyment . ##### Lexical entries (Greek & English) ex:graviera-el a ontolex:LexicalEntry ; </pre>

	<pre> lexinfo:partOfSpeech lexinfo:noun ; ontolex:canonicalForm [ontolex:writtenRep "γρᾰβιᾰῒῒῒᾰ"@el] ; ontolex:sense ex:graviera-sense-el . ex:graviera-en a ontolex:LexicalEntry ; lexinfo:partOfSpeech lexinfo:noun ; ontolex:canonicalForm [ontolex:writtenRep "graviera cheese"@en] ; ontolex:otherForm [ontolex:writtenRep "graviera"@en] ; ontolex:sense ex:graviera-sense-en . # Senses point to the shared concept (denotation) ex:graviera-sense-el a ontolex:LexicalSense ; ontolex:reference ex:GRAVIERA . ex:graviera-sense-en a ontolex:LexicalSense ; ontolex:reference ex:GRAVIERA . ##### Cross-lingual link (vartrans module) ex:graviera-tr a vartrans:Translation ; vartrans:source ex:graviera-el ; vartrans:target ex:graviera-en ; vartrans:category vartrans:exact . ##### Simple individuals used by the concept (could be SKOS too) ex:CheeseVariety a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "Cheese variety"@en . ex:Crete a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "Crete"@en . ex:Naxos a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "Naxos"@en . ex:Meze a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "meze"@en . ex:Dinner a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "dinner"@en . ex:HolidayMeal a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "holiday meal"@en . ex:Wine a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "wine"@en . ex:Pasta a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "pasta"@en . ex:Salad a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "salad"@en . ex:Authentic a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "authentic"@en . </pre>
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	<pre> ex:Traditional a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "traditional"@en . ex:Tasty a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "tasty"@en . ex:PDO a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "PDO"@en . ex:Nostalgia a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "nostalgia"@en . ex:Pride a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "pride"@en . ex:Enjoyment a skos:Concept ; skos:prefLabel "enjoyment"@en . </pre>
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Note: Two LexicalEntry nodes (Greek/English) share one concept (ex:GRAVIERA) via ontolex:reference. Frame alignment: the concept is tagged with ex:ConsumptionFrame; FE-like relations are modeled as object properties (e.g., ex:hasOrigin). Cross-lingual alignment uses vartrans (vartrans:Translation with vartrans:exact). One can later align ex:* properties to community ontologies (e.g., FrameNet, FoodOn, GeoNames) if desired.